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Development of a test bench to assess visual prostheses

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MASTER IN ENGINEERING OF COMPUTERS AND NETWORKS

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KEYWORDS: Visual prostheses, Artificial vision, Phosphene, Retinal Prosthesis (Epiretinal, Subretinal), cortical prosthesis, Optic Nerve/Tract Prosthesis, Stimulation, Implantation, CORTIVIS.

ABSTRACT:

Development the systems of visual prostheses by human Intervention to restore the functional vision . Blindness suffering has recently undergone a renaissance that has been fueled by a group or combination of celebrity and government interest and progress in the field of bioengineering which led to discover a neuroprosthetic system.

Blindness is generally considered as one of the most serious handicaps of the human beings. Due to the complexity of the visual system and despite numerous research efforts, rehabilitation developments in this field seem to be slow. However, this pessimistic picture might be changed soon since technological advances offer a whole new range of possibilities.

Several projects aim towards developing visual prostheses have been launched recently. Such devices would restore lost function by passing the damaged structures and electrically stimulating the remaining visual pathway. Obviously, damage of other structures should be avoided and the ‘artificial vision’ provided by the prosthesis has to be useful to the patient. A number of important factors (electrical, surgical, biocompatibility, psychophysical) have thus to be thoroughly investigated and considered.

This work intends to set the necessary background to understand visual perception in the context of artificial vision and the importance of the determination of minimum requirements for a visual prosthesis to restore useful vision. First, the basic anatomy and physiology of the visual system will be outlined and the basic issues of blindness and low vision will be discussed. Further along, the concept of visual prostheses will be explained in more detail. The different design approaches will be described, summarizing the current status of research.

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Contents

Chapter one: Introduction

Acknowledgment.....	(1)
Contents	(2)
Introduction	(5)
Problems & objectives	(7)
Project Structure.....	(7)
List of Figures	(8)

Chapter two: The visual system for humans

2.1 Overview.....	(11)
2.2 Anatomy and physiology of the human eye	(12)
2.2.1 Eye.....	(17)
2.2.1.1 Retina.....	(21)
2.2.2 Optic nerve and optic tract.....	(24)
2.2.3 Visual cortex	(27)
2.3 Visual impairment and blindness	(29)

Chapter three: Visual prostheses

3.1 Overview.....	(35)
3.1.1 Biological and technological considerations.....	(37)
3.2 History	(38)

3.3 Types of prostheses.....	(39)
3.3.1 Cortical Prosthesis.....	(39)
3.3.2 Optic Nerve/Tract Prosthesis.....	(40)
3.3.3 Retinal Prosthesis.....	(41)
3.3.3.1 Epiretinal Prosthesis.....	(42)
3.3.3.2 Subretinal Prosthesis.....	(46)

Chapter four: Electrical stimulation and implantation

4.1 Stimulation (History).....	(50)
4.2 Implantation.....	(52)
4.2.1 Cortical Implantation.....	(54)
4.2.1.1 Surface Cortical Stimulation.....	(55)
4.2.1.2 Intracortical Microstimulation.....	(57)
4.2.2 Optic Nerve Implantation.....	(60)
4.2.3 Retinal Implantation.....	(63)
4.2.3.1 Epiretinal Implantation.....	(63)
4.2.3.2 Subretinal Implantation.....	(66)

Chapter five: The currently researches worldwide

5.1 Visual Prosthesis Research Worldwide.....	(70)
5.2 Ongoing projects (currently).....	(72)
5.2.1 CORTIVIS.....	(72)
5.2.2 Argus Retinal Prosthesis.....	(75)

5.2.3 Microsystem-based Visual Prosthesis (MIVP).....	(78)
5.2.4 Implantable Miniature Telescope.....	(79)
5.2.5 Tübingen MPDA Project Alpha IMS.....	(80)
5.2.6 Artificial Silicon Retina (ASR).....	(81)
5.2.7 Photovoltaic Retinal Prosthesis.....	(82)
5.2.8 Bionic Vision Australia.....	(83)
5.2.9 Virtual Retinal Display (VRD).....	(84)

Chapter six: General conclusions

6.1 General conclusions	(87)
6.2 Future work and studies.....	(88)

Chapter seven: References

7 References	(91)
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Chapter one: Introduction

Introduction

The sight is considered as the most precious senses , the eye is a gem of the humans. Millions of people worldwide lose their eyesight due to a number of diseases or injury where the drugs or other therapies are not a solution. Some examples of these pathologies which affecting the sight are: cataracts, glaucoma, macular degeneration, retinitis pigmentosa, retinal detachment, eyeball loss by accident, etc. According to WHO (World Health Organization. Available on the web page: <http://www.who.int/en/>), as of 2014 it is estimated that there are 285 million people with visual impairments, from which 39 million are blind and 246 million have low vision. Ergo, millions of people could benefit from any kind of this the currently technology. In the case of total blindness, the type of implantation will vary depending on the point of visual track injured. And with the modern advancement in technology, partial restoration of sight is possible. Today, there are several kinds of implantation devices available for the blinds: retinal implantation divided into two types; subretinal implantation and epiretinal implantation, optic nerve implantation and Visual cortical implantation (VCI), all of them are still being tested. The most practical one is the visual cortical implantation ,specially developed in Europe (e.g. CORTIVIS). Due to its ability to restore vision for patients with a wide variety of blindness, where the visual cortex is intact. Such devices aim to restore function by direct electrical stimulation of neural tissue. This kind of approach has been proved to be very successful with cochlear implantations in the case of deafness. Several research groups have initiated projects, there purpose is to develop various visual prostheses and a huge effort is presently going on this field. The implantation of the first basic prototypes of visual prostheses demonstrates that the hope for a useful aid is within reach. There is increasing evidence that, some day, visual prostheses could bring similar benefits to blind people as those provided by cochlear implantation to deaf patients. To this date, most efforts in the field appear to be concentrated on the development of technical solutions for visual prostheses (microelectronics, biocompatibility, electrophysiology, etc...).

This review presents or identifies some of the basic operational characteristics of the visual system (Anatomy, physiology and etc...) as this knowledge is essential for the production a prosthetic device based on electrical stimulation through arrays of implanted electrodes, and discusses some of the advantages and disadvantages of the current approaches to restore vision. Central among these is our belief that the initial research in this area, which is in its infancy, so this should first be carried out the implantation or tests in animals, although there has been significant progress on many fronts since the first days of vision prostheses.

The progress made currently in developed test of visual prosthetic devices offers some hope to blind individuals. Plans for more sophisticated designs and increasing the number of electrodes offer the possibility of further improvements in function. Although the visual prostheses available at the present time are far from restoring normal vision, and restore some vision of a stable and functional for these blind individuals has been a major milestone in the treatment of severe vision loss and irreversible.

Existing mobility aids for the visually impaired such as canes, guide dogs and sonar glasses are available. However it is anticipated that the richness of sensory substitution would be much greater with a visual prosthesis. Visual prostheses may provide enough visual cues for blind people to perform every-day tasks such as navigation, recognition, and reading.

Problems & objectives

The main objective of the researches on the visual prostheses which being developed around the world is to develop simple image processing techniques that improve perception for users of electronic visual prostheses because of the growing numbers blinds and visually impaired for any reason, Considered as attempts to restore the functional vision in whose suffering from the blindness. Where millions of people around the world lose their eyesight due to a number of diseases or injuries where the drugs or other therapies are not a solution, according to WHO (World Health Organization) according to my explanation in the introduction. Although the visual prostheses available at the present time are far from restoring normal vision, and restore some vision of a stable and functional for these blind individuals has been a major milestone in the treatment of severe vision loss and irreversible. But this belief will disappear someday because of the results that have been obtained.

Project Structure

The project is structured to two main sections:

The first section: General background (from chapter 1 to chapter 2), while the second section: study the project (from chapter 3 to Chapter 5), followed by (Chapter 6) general conclusion.

So that the **chapter 1** deals with a general introduction to the work and a brief description of the problems and objectives . As the **chapter 2** deals with a simple introduction to the visual system for the human , anatomy of the eye and its parts in addition to visual impairment and blindness.

The second section: **Chapter 3** deals with a simple introduction to the title of the project (visual prostheses), its history, and types. **Chapter 4** contains on the stimulation and implantation of the visual prostheses . **Chapter 5** mentions the research projects around the world currently and explains every one of them.

List of figures

Figure (2.1):Anatomy of the Eye(right eye).....	(14)
Figure (2.2): Anatomy of the human eye.....	(19)
Figure (2.3a): The retina.....	(21)
Figure (2.3b): Simplified structure of the retina.....	(23)
Figure (2.4): The optic nerve.....	(24)
Figure (2.5): The optic tract.....	(26)
figure(2.6): The visual cortex.....	(28)
Figure (2.7): Major causes of blindness worldwide.Data taken from Thylefors(1995).....	(31)
Figure (2.8):Global distribution of blindness and its major causes,by economic region.....	(33)
Figure(3.1)Structure of Argus I device.....	(43)
Figure (3.2) Show the elements of Argus II device.....	(44)
Figure (3.3) This is colour photo of (Argus II)	(44)
Figure(3.4)Retina Implantation AG subretinal implantation.....	(47)
Figure(3.5)Retina implant ationAG subretinal implantation.....	(48)
Figure (4.1) Illustration of the visual pathway.....	(53)
Figure (4.2) Structure of a cortical implantation device.....	(54)
Figure (4.3) After implantation the X-rays of cortical visual prosthesis.....	(56)
Figure (4.4) A scanning electron micrograph of the 100 microelectrode.....	(58)
Figure (4.5) a scanning electron micrograph of the platinum coated tips of the UEA electrode.....	(58)

Figure (4.6) a drawing of the high velocity, impact insertion tool used to implant the UEA into cortical tissues.....(59)

Figure (4.7) Implanting intracortical prostheses..... (59)

Figure (4.8) illustrates the Electric stimulation to the optic nerve..... (60)

Figure (4.9) An Illustrates of the right optic nerve after implantation..... (61)

Figure (4.10) Implanted components (62)

Figure (4.11) Epiretinal implantation..... (64)

Figure (4.12) Subretinal implantation and its location in the retina (66)

Figure (4.13): General design of replacement of degenerated or lost photoreceptors by a MPDA which is positioned into the subretinal space..... (67)

Figure (5.1) World map that shows the global endeavor to develop of visual prostheses..... (71)

Figure (5.2) The general structure of the visual prosthesis (CORTIVIS)..... (74)

Figure(5.3):(A) A photograph of the external portion of the Argus II prosthesis system including glasses-mounted video camera, radio frequency (RF) coil, and Video Processing Unit (VPU) with rechargeable battery.(B) A photograph of the implanted portion of Argus II prosthesis system including the 6×10 electrode array, electronics case, and implant RF coil.....(76)

Figure (5.4) as shown in the image increasing resolution..... (77)

Figure (5.5) the micro-systems based visual prosthesis for optic nerve stimulation..... (78)

Figure (5.6) show size of IMT..... (79)

Figure (5.7) Elements of Photovoltaic Retinal Prosthesis..... (82)

Figure (5.8) (84)

Chapter two: The visual system for humans

2.1 overview

Studying and developing any subject should be done in details, accuracy and understanding, this chapter presents a brief overview of the human visual system, begins the discussion with an overview of the human eye, then describes the functions both of: the optic nerve/tract, the retina and ends with a quick overview of the visual cortex, also deals with the blindness and low vision (visual impairment). The human visual system can perform a number of images processing tasks in a manner vastly superior to anything we are able to do with the computers presently. If we want to mimic such processing, we need study carefully the way our eyes and brain do this.

The central nervous system is a dedicated device for information processing and full control over the movements and actions of the great structure of the human body "except the heart". And the visual system classifies an extension for central nervous system which gives the ability for organisms to visual information processing, as well as enable the formation of many of non-image functions photo response. It interprets and detects information from the visible light to building a representation of the surrounding environment of visual field. There are a number of the complex tasks performs visual system, including the reception of light and the formation of monocular representations; accumulation of the nuclear binocular perception from a pair of 2-dimensional projections. Identification and classification of the visual objects; assess distances between the objects; and guidance the body movements in the relation to the visual objects. The blindness is a psychological process of the visual information such as visual perception and a lack of. Non-image forming visual functions independent of the visual perception , including the pupillary light reflex (PLR)[1] and the circadian photo entrainment.

It uses a model of the human visual system, or so-called (HVS) model through image processing [2], computer vision experts and video processing and researchers to deal with the psychological and biological processes that are not fully understood yet. This form is used to simplify what behaviors is very complex system. It is necessary to think about the "benefit" of HVS model to produce desired effects. An example of taking advantage of HVS model include color TV.

Initially it was thought that the color TV required a very high bandwidth for the available technology. Then it was noticed that the color resolution of the HVS was much less than the resolution brightness; This allowed the color to be squeezed into the signal by chroma subsampling.

And many of HVS advantages are derived from evolution, when we need to defend ourselves or in search of food. We often see demonstrations of features HVS when we were looking at optical illusions.

2.2 Anatomy and Physiology of the Human Eye [3-4]

The Anatomy of the Eye

Even though the eye is small, only about 1 inch in diameter is an amazing complex structure, it serves the function of the sense of sight. Vision is the most used sense of the five senses and is one of the primary means that we use to gather information from our surroundings. More than 75% of the information we receive about the world around us consists of visual information.

The front of the human eye contains a curved lens, through which light reflected by objects in the surrounding environment passes. The light travels deep into the eyeball, passing all the way to the back of the eye, where it converges to a point. A unique set of cells at the back of the eye receives the light, harnessing its energy by converting it into an electrical impulse, or signal, then travels along neurons in the brain. The impulses are carried along a neuronal pathway that extends from the back of the eye all the way to the back of the brain, ultimately terminating in a region known as the visual cortex. There, the electrical signals from both eyes are processed and unified into a single image. The amount of time between the moment when light enters the eye and when a unified image is generated in the brain is near instantaneous, taking only fractions of a second.

The eye is often compared to a camera. Each gathers light and then transforms that light into a "picture." Both also have lenses to focus the incoming light. Just as a camera focuses light onto the film to create a picture, the eye focuses light onto a specialized layer of cells, called the retina, to produce an image.

The eyeball itself consists of three main layers; the outer layer, comprised of the cornea and the sclera, the middle layer, responsible for holding the blood supply for the eye as well as the iris and the pupil, and the inner layer, or the retina. Along with the three layers, there are also three chambers of fluid which are the anterior chamber, between the cornea and iris, the posterior chamber, between the iris and lens, and the vitreous chamber, which is between the lens and the retina. The first two chambers not only provide nourishment to the interior of the eye's structures, but also assist with inflation. The vitreous chamber contains a much thicker fluid called the vitreous humor. The vitreous humor gives the eye its shape and is the way by which light passes through before reaching the optic nerve. The optic nerve is the method of sending information and images to the brain. It runs from the back of the eyeball and through the optic foramen, where it connects with the brain. This nerve transmits the signals for vision to the brain making vision possible. There are also other nerves in the eye, most of which convey pain or control motor actions.

The eyelids are an external portion of the anatomy of the eye, which are mostly for protection and preservation. The eyelid carries lacrimal secretions from the tear glands across the eye as it blinks. This is to ensure moisture and provide minima protection. The eyelid is attached to the eye by a mucous membrane called the conjunctiva. Tear glands line the upper eyelid, which secrete tears for moisture. There are seven extraocular eye muscles attached to the outside the eyeball. Six are attached to the eyeball itself and the seventh is attached to the upper eyelid and is responsible for blinking. Blinking is a normal reflex involving the movement of the eye muscle attached to upper eyelid. The visual components of the eye are much more complicated in structure and function. The clear part of the eye is composed of the cornea, iris, and pupil. The white opaque part of the eye is the sclera, which surrounds the remaining portion of the eyeball. The sclera acts as a sheath for the optic nerve. The cornea and the sclera come together at the limbus, which contains many eye blood vessels. The iris and pupil are the most noticeable structures of the eye. The iris is the colored part of the eye composed of tissue lying underneath the cornea. The color of the eye, which is predetermined by genetics, also functions to block out unwanted light.

The pupil is located in the center of the iris. This is the entrance of light into the eye and changes size to control the amount of light let in.

The lens is located directly behind the iris and is used to focus light into the retina. The retina is light sensitive tissue containing photosensitive cells. These cells are known as rods and cones and use the light to convert it into electrical signals that the optic nerve carries to the brain. These cells add to the amazing nature of the human eyes. The fact that the eye uses light to form an image that makes sense to humans is miraculous.

Figure(2.1):Anatomy of the Eye(right eye)

<http://www.biographixmedia.com/human/eye-anatomy.html>

The Basic Anatomy of Vision

The human eye is developed directly from the brain and possesses two excellent lenses which are the cornea and the lens proper. When humans develop in the womb, the embryonic skin over the eye turns clear, becoming our cornea. In order to have complete clarity, this type of skin does not contain blood vessels, hair, and glands found in most other skin. It contains many nerves, causing it to be highly sensitive to touch.

The cornea is mostly a protective element for the eye, but also functions as a lens. The cornea has about four times the focusing power than the actual lens itself does.

The lens, much like the cornea, is made from embryonic skin and is also transparent; however it is able to change focus, which the cornea is not able to do. This function allows humans to focus on an object at any distance. A camera would focus by moving its hard lenses, but the human eye's lens is rubber like and flexes to focus quickly through changing its shape. As humans age, the lens loses flexibility which affects clarity and the ability to focus as compared to its original capabilities.

The anatomy of the retina is very important when investigating the complexity of the human eye. There are several layers in the retina that begin the task of processing light. The inner limiting membrane is the boundary between the vitreous humor, the clear gel that fills the space between the lens and the posterior aspect of the eye, and the retina. The ganglion layer is made of the cell bodies and the axons of the ganglion cells. There is also the inner plexiform layer contains the synapses between bipolar, horizontal, and amacrine cells. Next, the outer plexiform layer contains also bipolar and horizontal cells, and also receptor synapses. The outer nuclear layer comes next and contains the nuclei of the photoreceptor cells. The next layer is the outer limiting membrane, which contains a membrane that meets with the base of inner segments of the photoreceptor cells. Following the outer limiting membrane is the photoreceptor layer, comprised of inner and outer segments of rod and cone photoreceptors. The pigment epithelium layer comes next, which is comprised of dark pigmented cells, and appears dark due to its cells that contain melanin granules. Melanin granules absorb stray photons that can cause image blurs and protect certain cells from overexposure to light. The last layer is the choroid, which has much vascularization, and supplies the nutrients and oxygen to the retina.

The Basic Physiology of Vision

The retina is a piece of tissue that measures close to one half of a millimeter thick. This tissue lines the back of the inside of the eyeball. The tissue itself is developed from the embryonic forebrain, thus considered a part of the brain. The retina is one of the most important parts of the eye because it begins basic visual processing before the brain receives the information. There are three layers in the retina with packets of nerve cells arrayed in three rows and separated by two other layers containing synaptic connections. The retina's two most important functions are detecting and responding to light through sensory neurons and neural circuits. This begins the first stage of visual processing.

Cones and Rods are vital in light processing. In the outer segment layer, photopigment is seen in free floating disks in the rods and folded layers in the cones. Rods have discs, similar to stacked coins, while cones have a continuous outer membrane. The outer segments of the rods and cones are continuously replenished. This causes the pigment epithelium to trim off the excess of the membrane via phagocytic cells, which consume and recycle the material. Cones' disks are trimmed at dusk and rods at dawn, which is amazing considering that cones function best in bright light and rods function best in low light. The inner segment of the rods and cones contains support organelles, the nucleus, and the axon terminal. The axon terminal is the point where the neurotransmitter is released. The photopigment molecules in the disk membranes capture individual photons, which begins the neural signaling process. These photoreceptor cells are actually specialized hair cells that contain inner and outer segments, which are held together by the cilium.

There is a segment of the retina called the macula, located almost directly in the center of the retina. The macula is specialized for attaining acuity in straight ahead vision. Located in the macula is the fovea. In this area, cone density is the highest within the retina and rods are absent. These foveal cones are spaced tightly, in a honeycomb fashion. Altogether, the retina contains 120 million rods and 1 million cone photoreceptors.[3-4]

2.2.1 The Eye

The Arabic scientist *Ibn al-Haytham*(*Alhazen*), who was born in Basra-Iraq in 965 AD. The first to explain the eye combination, as he was the first who studied the entire anatomy of an autopsy, as well as he explained the functions of eye and its full organisms. Also Ibn al-Haytham proved several facts most notably that the light comes from objects and moving to the eye and not as it was customary at the antiquity from the eye to objects, It is also the most suitable to the principle of the invention the camera, Where is characterized Ibn al-Haytham the first who studied the psychological factors and the effects of vision.[5]

The human eye is described as the organ which gives us the sense of sight, allowing us to observe and learn more about the surrounding world than we do with any of the other four senses. We use our eyes in almost every activity we perform, whether reading, working, watching television, writing a letter, driving a car, and in countless other ways. Most people probably would agree that sight is the sense they value more than all the rest. The eye is composed of two spheres: a small portion of a strongly curved sphere making up the cornea and a large part of a not so strongly curved sphere. The adult eye measures about 2.5 cm in diameter. It is located at the front of the skull in a protected cone-shaped cavity called the orbit or the eye socket. The eye is surrounded by fatty connective tissue that provides protection and lubrication for movement. [6]

The eye allows us to see and interpret the shapes, colors, and dimensions of objects in the world by processing the light they reflect or emit. The eye is able to detect bright light or dim light, but it cannot sense objects when light are absent.

The eye is a fluid-filled sphere enclosed by three layers of tissue Figure (2.2). Most of the outer layer is composed of a tough white fibrous tissue, the sclera. At the front of the eye, however, this opaque outer layer is transformed into the cornea, a specialized transparent tissue that permits light rays to enter the eye. The middle layer of tissue includes three distinct but continuous structures: the iris, the ciliary body, and the choroid. The iris is the colored portion of the eye that can be seen through the cornea. It contains two sets of muscles with opposing actions, which allow the size of the pupil (the opening in its center) to be adjusted under neural control. The ciliary body is a ring of tissue that encircles the lens and includes a muscular

component that is important for adjusting the refractive power of the lens, and a vascular component (the so-called ciliary processes) that produces the fluid that fills the front of the eye. The choroid is composed of a rich capillary bed that serves as the main source of blood supply for the photoreceptors of the retina. Only the innermost layer of the eye, the retina, contains neurons that are sensitive to light and are capable of transmitting visual signals to central targets.

Figure (2.2): Anatomy of the human eye

<http://www.microscopy-uk.org.uk/mag/indexmag.html?http://www.microscopy-uk.org.uk/mag/artjun10/mol-eyes5.html>

In path to the retina, light passes through the cornea, the lens, and two distinct fluid environments. The anterior chamber, the space between the lens and the cornea, is filled with aqueous humor, a clear, watery liquid that supplies nutrients to these structures as well as to the lens. Aqueous humor is produced by the ciliary processes in the posterior chamber (the region between the lens and the iris) and flows into the anterior chamber through the pupil. A specialized meshwork of cells that lies at the junction of the iris and the cornea is responsible for its uptake. Under normal conditions, the rates of aqueous humor production and uptake are in equilibrium, ensuring a constant intraocular pressure. Abnormally high levels of intraocular pressure, which occur in glaucoma, can reduce the blood supply to the eye and eventually damage retinal neurons.

Fills the space between the back of the retina and the lens surface thick gelatinous substance called the vitreous humor, which represents about 80% of the size of the eye. In addition to maintaining the shape of the eye and vitreous humor contains phagocytic cells that operate on the removal of blood and other debris that might otherwise interfere with the transmission of light. Housekeeping capabilities of humor vitreous are limited, however, as a large number of individuals in the middle age and older with vitreal (floaters) will attest. Floaters are collections of very large debris consumption phagocytic so that remain to cast annoying shadows on the retina.

2.2.1.1 The Retina

The retina is a thin layer of tissue that lines the back of the eye from the inside (0.5 mm). It is located near the optical nerve. The purpose of the retina is getting focused lens of light, converting light into neural signals and sends these signals to the brain. Processes retina light through a layer of photoreceptor cells. These are basically light-sensitive cells, responsible for the detecting of the qualities such as color and light intensity. Retina processes information that has been collected by the photoreceptor cells and sends this information to the brain via the optic nerve. Basically, the retina processes a picture from the focused light, and left the brain to decide what is the picture. Due to the retina's vital role in vision, damage to the retina can cause permanent blindness. Can conditions such as retinal detachment, where abnormally retina is moved from its usual position, and prevent the retina from receiving or processing of light, and therefore prevents the brain from receiving this information, causing blindness.

Figure (2.3a): The retina

<http://webvision.med.utah.edu/book/part-i-foundations/simple-anatomy-of-the-retina/>

The retina presents a laminar structure (figure 2.3b) consisting of three layers of neural cell bodies or nuclear layers, and two layers of synaptic connections or plexiform layers. Additionally, an outer limiting membrane separates it from the choroid and an inner limiting membrane separates it from the vitreous chamber. The retinal pigment epithelium lays adjacent to the neural retina. Even though this melanin pigment has no neural tissue, its role is essential for optimal visual perception. Its main functions are: preventing light reflection, providing metabolic support for photoreceptors, and contributing to adaptation. The outer nuclear layer (ONL) constitutes the photosensitive coat of the retina formed by photoreceptor cells of two types: rods and cones. Cones function in bright light and are responsible for fine discrimination and color vision. Rods function in dim.

Figure (2.3b): Simplified structure of the retina. The retina is composed of three layers of neural cells and two synaptic layers surrounded by limiting membranes and the pigment epithelium[7-9]

<http://webvision.med.utah.edu/book/part-i-foundations/simple-anatomy-of-the-retina/>

2.2.2 The Optic nerve and Optic tract

The optic nerve and the optic tract are formed by the ensemble of axons of retinal ganglion cells and constitute the wiring of the visual system. Ganglion cell axons become myelinated at the optic disc, forming the optic nerve. The central artery and vein of the retina pass through its center. It has been suggested that there is a rough topographic representation within the optic disc and that visuotopic organization varies across the nerve's length[9].

The optic nerve in the back of the eye is located. It is also named the second cranial nerve or the second cranial nerve. It is the second of many pairs of the cranial nerves. Although the optic nerve is one of main parts of the eye, it is considered to be extension of the central nervous system. Transfer visual information from the retina to the vision centers of the brain via electrical impulses this is job of the optic nerve. The optic nerve is made of nerve cells or ganglionic cells. It consists of over (one million) nerve fibers. Our blind spot is caused by the absence of specialized photosensitive cells or photoreceptors, in the part of the retina where the optic nerve exits the eye. The most common illness affecting the optic nerve is Glaucoma. Glaucoma is caused when high intraocular pressure, or high pressure, is in the fluid in the eye (vitreous fluid). This high pressure compresses the optic nerve and causes cells to die, and is referred to as atrophy of the optic nerve.

Figure (2.4): The optic nerve

http://www.my-ms.org/anatomy_optic_nerve.htm

Optic tract is an extension of the optic nerve in the brain. It begins at the location where the information from the left eye and right eye through to create a complete picture. In fact the optic tract consists of two tracts: left optic tract and the right optic tract. Left optic tract transfer information from the retina temporal fibers from the left eye and nasal retinal fibers from the right eye. Right part of the optic tract transfer information from the temporal retinal fibers from the right eye and nasal retinal fibers from the left eye. Damage to the optic tract can lead to hemianopsia homonymous, a condition that causes a partial loss of sight. Stroke, congenital defects, tumors, infection, and surgery are all potential causes of hemianopsia homonymous. The damaged portion of the optical tract may be healed. However if it is not fully restore sight in 6 to 12 months, and the condition is likely permanent. Extenders prism peripheral vision therapy may help restore the patient to cope with damage to the optic tract.

Figure (2.5): The optic tract

http://www.theodora.com/anatomy/the_optic_nerve.html

2.2.3 The Visual Cortex

The visual cortex in the brain place dedicated to the integration as well as discrimination of the picture. This interpretation results in the conscious recognition of images as being a portrayal involving actuality. As outlined in figure (2.6).

The visual cortex could be divided into 3 large parts; occipital part which often receives the inputs from LGN and then transmits the outputs to dorsal and also ventral streams. The part of occipital contains the areas V1-V4 in addition to MT [10], which process different facets regarding of visual information and provides to a generic scene representation. The dorsal pathway is participate in analysis of space along with in and in action planning. The ventral pathway is participate object identify and categorization.

V1 is the primary cortical area which processes the visual info. It's sensitive to edges, gratings, line-endings, motions, color in addition to disparity (the difference angular between the projections of a point onto the right and left retinas). The most straightforward example of the hierarchical bottom-up processing could be the linear combination of the inputs through a number of ganglion cells with center surround receptive fields to create a representation of a bar. This is done through the simple cells of V1 and described first time by the prominent neuroscientists Wiesel along with Hubel. This type of the information integration means that the simple cells tend to be hypersensitive to the exact location of the bar and have a relatively small receptive field. The complicated cells of V1 receives the inputs from the simple cells, when also responding to the linear oriented patterns they're not sensitive to the exact position of the bar and have a larger receptive field. The computation present in this step could be a MAX-like the operation which in turn produces responses similar in amplitude to the larger of the responses pertaining to the individual stimuli. Many simple and complex cells may be also detect the end of a bar, and a small fraction of V1 cells are also be sensitive to local motion within their respective receptive fields.

The area V2 features more advanced or sophisticated contours representation such as texture-defined contours, illusory contours and also contours with border ownership. The area V2 also based upon the absolute disparity detection in V1 and also attributes cells which might be hypersensitive to relative disparity that is the difference between the absolute disparities of a

couple points in space. The final area is V4 receives the inputs from the area V2 and the area V3, but not much is known about the computation taking place in V3. Area V4 features neurons that are hypersensitive to contours with different curvature and vertices with distinct angles. An additional essential element is the coding for luminance-invariant hue. This is contrary to V1 in which neurons respond to color opponency along the a couple principle axis (red-green as well as yellow-blue) rather than the actual color. V4 additionally outputs for the ventral stream, to inferior temporal cortex (IT) which has been proven by way of lesion research being necessary for object discrimination.

figure(2.6): The visual cortex

<https://iis.uibk.ac.at/research>

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=M1iCrT2n6fY>

2.3 Visual impairment and blindness

Blindness is a state of visual perception has been attributed to physiological or neurological factors. Several standards have been developed to describe the extent of lost vision and blindness.[11] The total blindness is the complete absence of sensory perception of visible light and is medically known as NLP, which is an acronym for the lack of perception of light [12] and the is called, who is suffering from blindness of disabled people blind.

Some researchers believe that blindness may positively affect the audio capability, so that it becomes more accurate sense of hearing to distinguish sounds and musical tones, this is clearly evident when the animals as experimental mice when the difference in the strength of human Studying hearing as a result of loss of vision may not be clear.

Visual impairment can also be defined as any visual chronic deficit impedes the functioning of daily life and not correctable by ordinary glasses or contact lenses. Visual impairment can be mild or moderate, but also includes total blindness or functional blindness where no useful vision remains. Although there have been significant strides over the past few decades, and in the treatment and prevention of eye diseases that cause visual impairment, there are still many reasons for the loss of sight, which there is no cure.

Where normal vision is 20/20, and defined the legal blindness as visual acuity with best correction in the better eye worse than or equal to 20/200 or visual field extent of less than 20 degrees in diameter. In many states a visual acuity less than 20/40 to disqualifies person from obtaining a driver's license, as do some of the deficit in the visual field. The aim of the research in visual impairment and blindness in the development and assessing of new methods for the rehabilitation of the visually impaired individuals through assistive technologies, training, and rehabilitation services and education.

Blindness can be described as the absence of perception of visual stimuli. The international ICD-10[12] standard defines it as a visual acuity of less than 3/60 (0.05) in the better eye with the best possible correction. In parallel, low vision corresponds to a best-corrected visual acuity of less than 6/18 (0.3) but better or equal to 3/60. In 1990, the worldwide estimate of visually impaired

people was of 148 million. Of these, approximately 38 million people were blind, and 110 million were low vision cases at risk of becoming blind. Alarming, these numbers could double by the year 2020. To this date, however, the exact numbers remain unknown due to an important lack of epidemiological information. What we certainly know is that blindness represents a lot more than a mere health problem. On one hand, blind people usually face serious social constraints leading to poorer social lives, lower education levels, lower employment opportunities, and lower life expectancies than sighted people [13]. A 14-country study on disability ranked blindness as the fifth most disabling condition behind quadriplegia, dementia, active psychosis, and paraplegia [15]. On the other hand, the financial burden of blindness is considerable. Based on 1993 figures, it has been calculated as US\$168 billion [14]. The global economic productivity loss is estimated to grow from 19 billion in the year 2000 to US\$50 billion by the year 2020 if no preventive measures are taken [15].

Researchers say after the complexity of the visual system has been discussed, it is easy to realize that blindness or low vision can result from lesion or malfunction at any level of the visual pathway. The World Health Organization (WHO) has dedicated a set of fact sheets to blindness and its impact.

The major causes of blindness are exposed in figure (2.7). These are cataract, trachoma, glaucoma, and onchocerciasis (river blindness). Other diseases' impact is also acknowledged to be important, but specific numbers are unavailable to this date. Diabetic retinopathy is publicly documented as the primary cause of visual impairment amid working age adults. Age-related macular degeneration (AMD), disabling approximately 8 million people worldwide, constitutes the most common non-avoidable cause of visual disability.

Retinitis pigmentosa (RP) is the principal cause of inherited blindness with a prevalence estimated in 1 out of 3000. Statistics from Prevent Blindness America rank it as the 6th leading cause of blindness in the United States (4.7%) affecting approximately 100,000 Americans and approximately 1.5 million people worldwide. In addition, trauma is estimated to be responsible for half a million blindness cases.

Figure (2.7): Major causes of blindness worldwide. Data taken from Thylefors et al.(1995).

Causes of blindness vary significantly across economic regions (fig. 2.7). In developing countries most disabling conditions could be treated or prevented. Cataract can be successfully corrected with surgery; trachoma can be treated through hygiene, antibiotic administration, and corrective surgery; childhood blindness could be reduced by means of immunization, better nutrition, prophylaxis, and avoidance of harmful medicines (WHO, 2002). An ambitious initiative aiming to eradicate avoidable blindness through prevention and eye care programs, VISION 2020, has been launched by the WHO (2000).

In developed countries, like Switzerland, non-avoidable diseases are most common. The impact of these conditions, mainly age related, is expected to increase due to current trends of population ageing. Medical intervention is not expected to significantly reduce their impact in a near future since clinical treatments for the major diseases in this category are unavailable nowadays. Laser photocoagulation is roughly the only therapy available for AMD and benefits only a limited number of patients. Other experimental treatments for this disease like photodynamic therapy, pharmacologic inhibition, surgical intervention, and radiation therapy are being explored. Periodic screening and early laser treatment have proven to be helpful tools for preventing blindness in patients suffering from diabetic retinopathy, and alternative therapies are currently being studied. Genetic therapy is expected to be the best alternative for retinitis pigmentosa (RP).

In this context, the role of rehabilitation becomes crucial. Low vision and blindness aids for daily living have greatly evolved from guide dogs and canes to complex technological devices, although traditional methods are still greatly appreciated and frequently used. A number of studies have demonstrated the efficacy of these systems in improving quality of life and reducing perceived disability. New systems compensate the visual deficit either with augmentation devices (strong eyeglasses, telescopes, and video/computer magnifiers) or by sensory substitution (replacing vision with another sense such as hearing or touch). The variety of the available aids is enormous; a simple internet search will return plenty of references and good overviews of such systems can be easily found in the literature.

The global distribution of blindness by major causes (cataract, trachoma, glaucoma, and other) reported by Thylefors et al. Show the distribution by economic regions (Fig. 2.8).

Figure (2.8): Global distribution of blindness and its major causes, by economic region. EME = established market economies; FSE = former socialist economies; OAI = other Asia and islands; SSA = sub-Saharan Africa; LAC = Latin America and Caribbean; MEC = Middle Eastern crescent.

As of 2014 there were 285 million visually impaired people in the world, of which 246 million had low vision and 39 million were blind. The majority of people with poor vision are in the developing world and are over the age of 50 years as I mentioned previously.

Chapter three: Visual prostheses

3.1 Overview

After more than four decades of research visual prostheses are moving from the study (laboratory) into the application (clinic). These devices are designed to provide prosthetic vision to the blind who have lost their sight fully or partially by stimulating localized neural populations in one of the retinotopically organized structures of the visual pathway, usually the retina or visual cortex.

A visual prosthesis generally described that a bionic eye or even that the device can be a successful alternative to the drugs aren't useful for the treatment of most cases of loss of sight, is an experimental visual device aims to restore functional vision those suffering from partial or total blindness. Have been developed of a variety of devices, usually modeled of a cochlear implant or bionic devices a type of neural prosthesis in use considering that the mid of 1980s. The concept of using an electric current (for instance, electrically stimulates the retina as well as the visual cortex) to provide the sight dates back to the 18th century, that have been discussed by some scientists and researchers including Benjamin Franklin et al.

Electronic visual prostheses have proved the possibility to restore a primitive sensation of the vision to blind individuals on shaped a small light spots or halos of light called (phosphene). Now the retinal implantation has been tested in humans through four groups independent. Also the optic nerve and cortical implantation has been evaluated in humans. The initial implants have attained results remarkable , including detection of motions and also distinguishing objects from a set. To improve on these types of final results, several studies groups have performance simulations which estimate approximately 1000 individual pixels may be was required to regain considerable capabilities such as face recognition and reading. In order to achieve a device which could stimulate the visual system in this many locations, issues related of power consumption and electronic packaging must be resolved.

Generally, three major types of visual prostheses are currently being developed in laboratory and applied in clinic; the stimulation of visual cortex using cortical implants[16],retinal devices [17] implanted in the subretina or epiretina, and stimulation of the optic nerve [18-19]which will be explained in (chapter 4) "implants and simulation of visual prostheses". The optic nerve serves as a compact conduit for all the information in the visual scene, which means that electrical stimulation of a small area of the optic nerve would be expected to activate a large segment of the visual field. Thus the optic nerve of visual prosthesis could be a potential choice for a visual prosthesis design.

The progress made currently in development test of visual prostheses devices have ability to offers some hope to blind individuals. Strategies regarding a lot more innovative designs and also increasing the number of electrodes offer the possibility of further improvements in function. In spite of the visual prostheses are available at the present time are far from restoring the normal vision, and restore some vision of a stable and functional for these blind individuals has been an important milestone in the treatment of severe vision loss and irreversible.

3.1.1 Biological and Technological considerations

Biological considerations

The possibility to give the sight to a blind individual by using a bionic eye depends on the circumstances surrounding from the loss of sight whenever were nerve and retina intact whenever the results were better and less chances of success if it was the cause of blindness before birth or genetically. For the retinal prostheses which are considered the most common visual prostheses under development (because of easy access to the retina), there are some disease that patients with vision loss due to degeneration of photoreceptors such as (retinitis pigmentosa RP, choroideremia, geographic macular atrophy degeneration) are the best candidate for the treatment. The candidates for visual prostheses implants find the procedure most successful if the optic nerve was developed prior to the beginning of blindness. The persons who are born with blindness may lack a fully developed optical nerve, which typically is develops prior to birth.

Technological considerations

Although high costs in the study and development of visual prostheses are currently being developed as a probably valuable aid for individuals with the visual degradation. there are a lot of studies for example Argus II (will be described it in chapter (5)), manufactured by company Second Sight for Medical Products where is the only such device to have received the marketing approval (also CE Mark in Europe in 2011), all of other efforts still in investigational, and most of them have not yet issued it to any clinical use in the patients.

3.2 History

Some researchers may differ about history of visual prosthesis, and when began the idea of the simulation?, and who is discovered it?, was the muscle stimulation that discovered by the Egyptians in 2500 BC is an indicator to exploit this property (stimulation) as I browsed in (<http://www.healthline.com/natstandardcontent/alt-electroanalgesia>)?, many questions comes to the mind of the researcher.

Indeed the human body is a network of nerves through which is a human controlled on all his actions, as well as the eye is composed of nerves that travels through which the optical signal after converted into an electrical signal by the retina and visual cortex up to and there are processed to form an image.

Generally the history of visual prosthesis dates back to the understanding of the electrical stimulation on the human tissues in 1799 by Foerster a German neurosurgeon.who in 1929 proved that the electrical stimulation for the visual cortex could lead to the perception of light spot (phosphene). Also the idea of prosthetic electronic device could be traced to the patent granted to an Australian, Tassicker Graham, who described how in 1956 described in a photosensitive selenium cell and placed back the retina of a patient blind in phosphenes. [20] in the 1960s and 1970s, BRINDLEY [21] and Dobell [22] a pioneer in the field of the artificial vision through the implant electrodes in the visual cortex and which indicates that they were able to induce consistent named "phosphenes". Around that time Uematsu also to investigate the feasibility of visual prosthesis and was able to evoke "phosphenes" which fluttered or blinked and some which remained stable in position. Phosphenes evoked also varied from the simple white to complex multi-coloured patterned. [23]

More development in this field was limited until the year 1990s when advances in biomaterials, electronics, micro-fabrication and retinal surgery led to a series of the developments in this field which focused mainly on the artificial retina but also in the miniaturization of cortical stimulating devices. [16][24] Carried out the preclinical investigations in this decade would lead to a large number of clinical experiments and trials in the decade begin from 2000 to the 2010.

Currently have two retinal prostheses devices are in a large scale clinical trials with evidence of functional vision proved well. These are the most advanced and studies prostheses to date and details of them, epiretinal one and the other subretinal.

3.3 Types of prostheses

3.3.1 Cortical Prosthesis

As I mentioned earlier in history of visual prosthesis the cortical prosthesis begins in 1929 when Foerster investigated the effects of electrical stimulation of the occipital lobe of the human cortex [25]. He found that this stimulation caused a subject to "see" a small point of light, later called it term a "phosphene". This result was reproduced many times after the original experiment with both sighted subjects and blind subjects. The idea that the concurrent stimulation of many sites in the brain can be produce a single coherent image was postulated as early in 1953 by Krieg. He thought it would be possible to use this technique to restore sight to the blind. Because there is rough retinotopy in the visual cortex.

There are many current models of the intracortical prosthesis include:(Utah electrode array [26] and the Illinois Intracortical Visual Prosthesis project [27]).The Utah device consists of multiple silicon spikes organized in a square grid measuring(4.2 x 4.2 mm) with a platinum electrode at the tip of each spike. The Illinois device consisting of 152 intracortical microelectrodes, has been chronically implanted in an animal model and the model for human implantation has been proposed. [26-27]

The cortical visual prosthesis is advantageous over other approaches as it bypasses all diseased visual pathway neurons rostral to the primary visual cortex. However, the disadvantages are the histological changes induced by a chronically implanted cortical prosthesis which needs to be investigated. The organisation of the visual field is very complex at the level of the primary

cortex than at the retina or optic nerve. It is not easily reproducible between various patients and there is a high level of cortical specialisation of various parameters including colour, motion, and eye movement [28]. Finally the surgical complications of this approach carry significant morbidity and mortality for the patient.

3.3.2 Optic Nerve/Tract Prosthesis

There is good news for patients who suffering from blindness in retinal ganglion, because researchers have found hope potential for implant in this type as it will be discussed later. In patients who are blind with functional retinal ganglion cells, the optic nerve is an alternative to electrical stimulation. However to achieve unraveling and stimulation exact reticular distribution within its challenge. The researchers began by targeting the optic nerve as a potential site for the implantation of a visual prosthesis. Among them is Veraart [29], have attempted this method by employing the concept of a spiral nerve cuff electrode. An electrode cuff is surgically implanted circumferentially on the external surface of the optic nerve. Since the device does not penetrate the optic nerve sheath, it relies on the principle of retina topic organisation within the optic nerve. Recently, optic nerve prosthesis with four electrodes has been implanted into a patient human. The optic nerve is an appealing site for the implementation of a visual prosthesis as the entire visual field is represented in a small area which can be reached surgically and presents a viable anatomic location for an implant. However, the optic nerve is a densely consolidated neural structure with approximately (1.2 million axons in a 2 mm diameter cylinder). Surgical manipulation of this area requires dissection of the dura, with an inherent risk of infections and possibly interruption of blood flow to the optic nerve [26]. The optic nerve and the retinal ganglion cells (RGC) represent higher- order structures than the bipolar cells targeted by the retinal prosthesis. As such the processing power of the bipolar, amacrine and horizontal cells is lost and therefore much more image processing must be achieved by the implant rather than relying on intact human physiologic pathways.

Lastly the nerve fibres from the macula lie most centrally within the optic nerve. The cuff electrodes are thus, further away from the macular fibres and this will dramatically limit the use

of this approach. Investigators have proposed intraneuronal stimulation devices in order to target individual neurons within the optic nerve more accurately [26].

Recently Veraart [30] published results of an optic nerve prosthesis chronically implanted in a blind volunteer of (RP) with no residual vision. The volunteer underwent performance evaluation during the course of a training programme. The results were encouraging in that the blind volunteer was able to interact with the environment adequately while demonstrating pattern recognition and a learning effect for processing time and orientation discrimination.

3.3.3 Retinal Prosthesis

As for the retinal prosthesis, it give hope for patients with retinal degenerative diseases, because the photoreceptors and neighboring tissue degenerate, the retina's output cells remain largely intact and ease of access for it and there are large number of research about them .There are 20–25 million people around the world who are blind or facing blindness due to these diseases and they have few treatment options [31]. Drug therapies are able to help a small fraction of the population, but for the vast majority their best hope is through prosthetic devices.

These diseases cause a progressive loss of the retina's input cells the photoreceptors, which leads to severe visual impairment. While the photoreceptors and neighboring tissue degenerate, the retina's output cells remain largely intact. Prosthetic devices make use of this. The approach is to bypass the damaged tissue and provide direct stimulation to the surviving cells, driving them to send visual information to the brain. The devices have not yet achieved the success that was hoped for. Current devices still provide only very limited vision. For example, they allow patients to see spots of light and high contrast edges, which provide some ability for navigation and gross feature detection, but they are far from providing patients with normal representations of faces, landscapes and etc. [32]

Retinal prostheses can be categorized based on its location into epiretinal and subretinal prosthesis:

3.3.3.1 Epiretinal Prosthesis

From its name, differs from the other one because of its location on the surface of the retina. Epiretinal prosthesis rely on imaging devices such as a camera and then transform this visual information to patterns of electrical stimulation to excite remaining viable retinal neurons. Current device of the epiretinal prostheses is (ArgusII) consists of three main components: the first component captures images of light using a camera put on the glasses, and the second component transforms this image into electrical stimulation external laptop patterns, and the third component, which lies on the inner surface of the retina, then stimulate the remaining cells in the retina inner.[33]and there are a variety of epiretinal devices being developed there.[34-38] only three devices that are in advanced stages of development will be described. The most advanced retinal prosthesis project at the present time is (Argus II) epiretinal implant developed by Second Sight Medical Products Inc., based in California (Will be described in Chapter 5). The first generation model of the device (Argus I) consisted of an intraocular epiretinal multielectrode array measuring 250–500 mm with 16 platinum micro electrodes(Fig3.1) developed thereafter to (Argus II).[39]

Figure (3.1) Structure of Argus I device [45]

In 2007 the US Food and Drug Administration approved the second generation (Argus II) retinal prosthesis system using an epiretinal implant for clinical study in humans (Figure 3.2). The Argus II implant component consists of 60 independently controllable electrodes (Figure 3.3).

Figure (3.2) Show the elements of Argus II device [45] [49]

Figure (3.3). This is a coloured photo of (Argus II) epiretinal prosthesis secured to the retina with a retinal tack.

The advantages of the epiretinal approach include the following; the vitreous acts as a sink for heat dissipation from the microelectronic device; a minimal number of microelectronics are incorporated into the implantable portion of the device; the wearable portion of electronics allows for easy upgrades without requiring subsequent surgery and the electronics allow the user and the doctor full control over every electrode parameter and digital signal processing involved in imaging objects, allowing the implant to be customized for each patient.

The disadvantages of this approach include the requirement of technology to provide prolonged adhesion of the device to the inner retina, and increased current requirement due to greater distance of the target bipolar cells from epiretinal device than with the subretinal device.

3.3.3.2 Subretinal Prosthesis

The second type of retinal development is the subretinal prosthesis, which developed in Germany ,but the development faces some disadvantages and difficulties, for example the limited subretinal space to place electronics as well as the close proximity of the retina to the electronics which would increase the risk of thermal injury to the neurons.

Subretinal prostheses involve implantation of the prosthetic device between the retina most likely the bipolar cell layer and the Retinal Pigment Epithelium. Access to the subretinal space can be either: ab externo (scleral incision) or: ab interno (through the vitreous cavity and retina).Have developed two of the subretinal implants at a very good level.

The earliest retinal prosthesis is (subretinal prosthesis), Artificial Silicon Retina (ASR), developed by Optobionics company. [40-42] and ASR is 2 mm in diameter and 25 mm in thickness. Is a device optobionic, and this means that the energy required by the retinal prosthetic devices is derived from the incident light and is composed of about 5000 independently functioning electrode tipped microphotodiodes. The electric charge produced by ASR to change the potential of the retinal nerve cell membrane and connect the light to simulate how the design that the activation of these cells to form images usually visual retinotopic.

Implant retina AG which was founded in early 2003 in the (Tubingen, Germany), developed initially implant optobionic microphotodiode array consisting of microprocessors in 7000 with the configuration of checker-board pattern. [43-44] and the implant in animal models has been used, but they discovered that would generated from microphotodiode energy array there was insufficient [45-47] and an additional source of power would be needed. A compound visual prosthesis device was developed .This consists of three parts: subretinal, extraocular and subdermal (Figs. 3.4-5).

<http://royalsocietypublishing.org/content/early/2010/11/01/rspb.2010.1747>

Figure (3.4) Retina Implant AG subretinal implant[48-49]

<http://www.medgadget.com/2013/02/retinal-implant-alpha-ims.html>

Figure (3.5) Retina implant AG subretinal implant[48-49]

Advantages of the subretinal prosthesis include closer proximity to the next surviving neurons to the visual pathway and therefore less current requirement and the lack of a mechanical means of fixation.

The disadvantages include the limited subretinal space to place electronics as well as the close proximity of the retina to the electronics which would increase the risk of thermal injury to the neurons.

Chapter four: Electrical stimulation and implants

4.1 Stimulation (History)

The first notes about the electric stimulation in the visual cortex began in "Germany" By the end of the First World War, during the neural surgical operations using anesthesia local. At the 1918 it was found that static dots of the light, after that called “phosphenes” could possibly be seen in the patients contralateral visual fields through of the stimulating surface of visual cortex .Since long time dream of treatment blindness began in the early 1960s with Dr. Giles Brindley in England research and culminated in year 1968 when implanted in one of a blind volunteer an electrodes array of 80 it stimulates electrodes against the visual cortex of right half of brain. Dr.Brindley shown that it was able or possible to transfer external visual information into the patient’s mind, so that may identify uncomplicated patterns and letters through combinations of multiple “phosphenes”. The results of his works had been published within a scientific document in 1969 which usually grew to become a landmark in visual researches. [21]

Also may be say, have originated the first results of the stimulation from idea to stimulate the nerves with regard for therapeutic purposes. The first use recorded of electrical stimulation to relief pain dates back to the (46 AD), when used Scribonius Largus torpedo fish (electric rays) to relieve headaches. [50] At the end of the 17th century, the muscles of dead frogs legs twitched when struck by a direct current on the nervous system that discovered by Luigi Galvani. [51] In 1870 the modulation of the brain activity by electrical stimulation of the motor cortex in the dogs was found that resulted in limb movement. [52] Many milestones have been developed from the end 18th century to nowadays. At this present time sensory prostheses devices, such as cochlear implants, visual implants, implants middle of auditory brain , and spinal cord stimulators and also motor prostheses devices, such as Bion micro-stimulators, deep brain stimulators, the brain control and sensing interface, and heart electric stimulation devices are widely used. Add to that the ancient Egyptians were the first to use the muscle simulation.

Neurostimulation

Neural stimulation can be described as therapeutic activation of part of the nervous system by using the microelectrodes. In order to restore a sense the electrodes are used to interface with the excitable tissue, such as a cochlear implant to hearing or to control the organ, such as a pacemaker.

Neurostimulation technology improves the quality of life such as those who are completely paralyzed or suffering from deep losses to the different sense organs. It acts as a key part of the neural prosthetic for vision artificial, hearing aids, prostheses and brain-machine interfaces. In a state of nervous stimulation, and mostly an electrical stimulation is used and charge-balanced biphasic constant current waveforms or capacitively coupled charge injection approaches are adopted. Instead, as a non-invasive method in which a magnetic field which causes neurostimulation the transcranial magnetic stimulation has been proposed.

4.2 Implants:

As I mentioned in many previous times, where many of the recent studies have shown that electrical stimulation of the visual cortex makes the blind see Multi-phosphene (spot light). It was also observed that the spatial location of the phosphene” is affected by the location of electrical stimulate over the cortex. Consequently it was concluded that it is possible to create light perception in blind people by stimulating a small area of neurons along the visual pathway. So all of the present visual prostheses are based on this principle. The establishment of the current artificial vision systems through electrical stimulation at different locations along the visual pathway in the central nervous system. Electrical stimulation of neurons makes them open voltage-sensitive ion channels. And thus reach the cell action potentials and impulse passed to the next neuron. There are several implants that can be used to restore vision that according to their locations are named along this pathway, (figure 4.1) (cortical, optic nerve, subretinal and epiretinal). Different diseases require a different approach towards the restoration of vision. Diseases that result from outer retinal degeneration (age-related macular degeneration and retinitis pigmentosa RP) can be reversed through electrical stimulation of the retina or optic nerve. The Whole thickness of retinal diseases and diseases of the optic nerve and loss of the eye, diseases of the central nervous system, can be reversed through the cortical implant. Regardless of the artificial implants along the visual pathway in the brain there is another type of artificial visual system called vOICe [53]. It translates the video image to the sounds, and in this way a blind person can see with his / her eyes touched for this type of visual system just for mention.

Figure (4.1) Illustration of the visual pathway

http://thebrain.mcgill.ca/flash/d/d_02/d_02_cr/d_02_cr_vis/d_02_cr_vis.html

This section briefly describes the different types of prostheses (Implants) being researched today.

4.2.1 Cortical Implant

In visual cortical implants (VCI), only the visual cortex has to be intact. Unlike the other implants, the retina and optic nerve can be degraded or damaged. As shown in Figure (4.2) shows the main structure for cortical implants. By a camera integrated into the eyeglass frames which follows the eye movements the image is captured. After that via a transcutaneous link that stimulates the microelectrodes implanted in the visual cortex the image is transferred and results into the creation of an image [54].

Figure (4.2) [54] Structure of a cortical implant device: Concept of an intracortical visual prosthesis. A camera captures the image and transmits stimulation patterns through a transcutaneous link. Stimulation of microelectrodes implanted in the visual cortex results in a perception of the image. In a practical system, the camera would be integrated into eyeglass frames and tied to eye movements.

There are two type of cortical implants can interaction with the brain;either Intracortical (direct) or Epicortical(indirect):

4.2.1.1 Epicortical Stimulation (Surface Cortical)

The experiments with stimulation of the visual cortex in the period between the late sixties and early seventies the earliest were done by BRINDLEY and Dobbie. They were stimulated visual cortex by placing the electrodes over the surface, because it was supposed to process this area visual signals from the eye (figure 4.3). By using this method they were able to evoke spot light called "phosphenes", but noted that multiple phosphenes were created by one and the same electrode and that the created phosphenes were inconsistent. As has been the use of large electrodes with electrodes were spaced 3MM and the currents of 1-3 mA. Also Dobbie concluded that the brightness of the phosphene is logarithmic function of the current amplitude of the stimulating devices.

Figure (4.3) after implantation the X-rays of cortical visual prosthesis [55]

4.2.1.2 Intracortical Microstimulation(ICMS)

In the early of seventies the first studies in "Intracortical Implants" were done by the National Institutes of Health. They were implanted microelectrodes directly in the visual cortex. The tip sizes of the microelectrodes were close to the sizes of the neurons, and by this way the control of the neuron function could be achieved by more selective stimulation. Using this type of the implant, arrays of smaller electrodes were created, stimulating a smaller surface area on the visual cortex and using lower current thresholds. Thus, predictable forms of phosphenes were observed and the interactions between the different phosphenes were reduced [54]. One of the most known Intracortical Implant, called "Utah" electrode array (UEA) Figure (4.4), was developed by the University of Utah. They used silicon, which is highly biocompatible, as electrode material. In same university large number of 1.5mm long electrodes was separated from each other by 0.4mm space. Their tips (figure 4.5), 80-100 microns in diameter at their basis, were covered with platinum. One of the most important design considerations was that the array had to be very thin since it had to stay on the surface of the brain and not interact with the skull. Because of its smaller size, a special surgical techniques and tools had to be developed that facilitate the implantation of the intracortical implant in the visual cortex. Thus a pneumatically activated insertion tool was created figure (4.6). It was able to insert the array into the cortical tissue in 200 μ s and not damage the tissue. [56]

Figure (4.4) a scanning electron micrograph of the 100 microelectrode, Utah electrode array (UEA) [56]

Figure (4.5) a scanning electron micrograph of the platinum Coated tips of the UEA electrodes [56]

Figure (4.6) a drawing of the high velocity, impact insertion tool
Used to implant the UEA into cortical tissues [56]

Figure (4.7) Implanting intracortical prostheses [54]

4.2.2 Optic Nerve Implant

Wrote M.E. Brelen and colleagues, University Catholique Louvain.[57] "To make the optic nerve visual prosthesis more acceptable, implantation techniques safer and less invasive than those previously used have been developed. A medial transconjunctival approach is now used to implant a stimulating electrode around the intraorbital section of the optic nerve. This new technique allows sufficient exposure of the nerve after detaching only one rectus muscle and performing a lateral canthotomy. Previously, an electrode was implanted in the intracranial part of the optic nerve, which required more invasive surgery. The new technique was first developed in cadavers and in patients undergoing eye enucleations. Finally a 68-year-old blind man suffering from retinitis pigmentosa underwent long-term implantation". This is what wrote by M.E. Brelen and colleagues.

On the other hand the optic nerve is stimulated electrically through stimulators connected externally, in the implants of the optic nerve. The optic nerve stimulations results into phosphene sensitivity over a broad segment of the visual field. As shown in the figure (4.8), were taken the image by the camera and an electrode array stimulates the optic nerve. After a certain period of training, the person with the optic nerve implant to be able to form recognition, spatial localization, motion detection, and color vision.

Figure (4.8) illustrates the Electric stimulation to the optic nerve

Figure (4.9) An Illustrates of the right optic nerve after implantation. [55]

In the Figure (4.9) refers a proximate drawing of a right optic nerve after implantation. The cuff electrode array was implanted intercranial. A cable is passed through the skull and under the skin and down of the outer surface of the skull. And then it is passed along the neck to leave the skin below the clavicle. There are no acute or chronic side effects from this optic nerve implant of stimulating the electrodes in human. [55]

Figure (4.10) implanted components. [58]

In the figure (4.10) is illustrated an x-ray of the spiral cuff silicon rubber electrode which is implanted intercranial. The chronic implantation of optic nerve spiral cuff electrode, neurostimulator, and antenna are proved to be very safe medical and surgical procedures. To this point, the equipments used for optic nerve implants are proved to be biocompatible and well-designed in the biological environment. They are very suitable and efficient for generation of electrical stimulation on the optic nerve [58-59].

4.2.3 Retinal Implant

There are three types of retinal implants currently in clinical trials: epiretinal Implants (on the retina), subretinal Implants (behind the retina), and suprachoroidal implants (above the vascular choroid). In this type of implants prosthetics the stimulation electrodes are placed on the patient's retina. Retinal implants provide the user with low resolution images by electrically stimulating surviving retinal cells. Such images may be sufficient for restoring specific visual abilities, such as (light perception and object recognition).

But in fact now I will deal with into two types from this retinal implants:

4.2.3.1 Epiretinal Implant

Implants are being researched as a viable way to restore vision in patients suffering from retinal pigmentosa as well as macular degeneration. The first condition to place an epiretinal implant, the ganglion cells have to be intact. In the Figure (4.11) shows a typical epiretinal implant along with its external support system. Since the epiretinal implant requires the ganglion cells for stimulation.

The epiretinal implant consists of two parts the first an intraocular unit and the second is extraocular unit. The extraocular unit consists of a video camera, a video processor, a telemetry encoder chip, and radio frequency amplifier (all mounted on a pair of glasses, and a primary induction coil mounted on the eye). And the glass lenses provide a link to a battery powering the system. The camera mounted on the glass captures the image and the processor performs edge extraction, motion and other image processing tasks. The image is translated into pixels then sent to a chip implanted in the eye of patient.

Figure (4.11) Epiretinal implants

<http://arstechnica.com/science/2012/08/sight-for-sore-eyes-optical-prosthetic-mimics-retina-functionality/>

The Power is transferred to the place of implant via a primary coil, which has been proved to be inefficient. An infrared laser can be used instead of it, but that poses a threat of damaging the eye if the laser is misaligned.

The intraocular unit consists of a secondary coil or a photovoltaic receiver to capture the laser, a receiver and regulator, a retinal simulator with a telemetry protocol decoder, a simulating signal array and an electrode array. All of the elements can be either combined on a single chip implanted above the retina, or in two different chips with the simulating and electrode arrays placed above the retina [60-62].

The advantage of the epiretinal implant is that the implant is off the retinal surface and exists in the vitreous cavity, contrary of subretinal, which contains the vitreous fluid that helps dissipate the heat generated by the implanted electronics.

And the disadvantages include the risk at the time of attaching the epiretinal implant to the retina. The implant experiences rotations of speeds of more than 400 degrees/second, due to the movement of the eyeball. There are many methods to attach the implant, including retinal tacks, but they are still under investigation. And there are another disadvantage is the non-focal widespread stimulation. The implant is placed on top of ganglion cell axons, which are in close proximity to each other, making stimulating particular axons difficult, and the task of encoding the image tricky since many ganglion cells will be stimulated at once. Also it is unknown how much power can be transmitted wirelessly to the implant without raising the temperature of the eye and thus damaging it [61-62].

4.2.3.2 Subretinal Implant

Considered the subretinal implant is the most successful of the vision implants. Patients with In Retinitis pigmentosa disease and the retinal pigment epithelial cells (RPE) begin to die out and the person begins losing the vision gradually. Since the function of the retina to transduce light into biological signal is weakened, it causes blindness. Subretinal implant is used to substitute the lost (RPE) cells with the ones of artificial basis to restore the vision. But the remainder of the retina is intact. This means that the horizontal, bipolar and amacrine cells are still viable. Subretinal implant aims at replacing the photoreceptors in the retina .It is implanted in the subretinal space, where the damaged photoreceptors are found, between the retina and the pigment epithelium. In the Figure 2.3 depicts a typical subretinal implant [60-62].

Figure (4.12) Subretinal implant and its location in the retina.[62]

A microphotodiode array (MPD), a silicon micromanufactured device, or semiconductor microphotodiode array (SMA) is used in this type of the implant. This piece of equipment is placed behind the retina between the sclera and the bipolar cells. The incident light is transformed into electrical potentials that excite the bipolar cells to form an image sensation .in figure (4.13) is shown the general design of replacement of degenerated or lost photoreceptors by MPDA . There are specific priorities which must be taken care by subretinal implant in order to be functioning well to restore the vision: the devise has to be biocompatible so that it would be used for long-term performance.

Figure (4.13): General design of replacement of degenerated or lost photoreceptors
By a MPDA which is positioned into the subretinal space. [63]

The subretinal implant consists of a photodiode array, circuitry to generate pulses that would stimulate the retina, and an electrode array. The chip needs no external power supply, it has a solar array that is powered by the incident light entering the eye.

Subretinal implants are simple and form a stand-alone unit but there are reason "remote of location" will deal it currently. Light entering the eye stimulates the photodiode array and induces the solar array to provide power. The photodiode array then drives the pulse generation circuitry. This circuit provides pulses that are proportional to the intensity of the light. The more intense the light, the higher the frequency of the pulses. The pulses are then sent to the electrode array which stimulates the bipolar and horizontal cells.

The disadvantage to the subretinal implant is its remote location in the subretinal space. This makes it hard to supply external power, if not using a solar array, or to monitor the device if needed. Also, the implant comes in contact with retinal cells and tissues, which could cause damage. Furthermore, the subretinal space does not provide a means to dissipate the heat generated by the implant. This type of implant is also the most limited prosthetic, where the patient has to have most of the retina intact [61].

Chapter five: The currently researches worldwide

5.1 Visual Prosthesis Research Worldwide

Research efforts around the world to develop a prosthetic visual micro-electronic aims to restore vision for the blinds .Different of visual prostheses using neural stimulation techniques targeting different locations along the visual pathway are currently being follow-up. Retinal prosthesis has proved to be able to display blind subjects in the advanced stages of outer retinal diseases opportunity to restore some of the visual function. With the relatively low density implants retina, visual simple tasks that are impossible with blind subject's natural light perception vision can be achieved. Blind subjects can spatially resolve individual electrodes within the array of retinal prosthesis implanted and the system can be used to distinguish and identify patterns oriented.

Since BRINDLEY caused a sensation visual in a blind patient by electrical stimulation of the visual cortex, and some groups have been committed to the development of the visual prosthesis based on the electrical stimulation over the remaining structures of the visual pathway to restore lost vision caused by age-related macular degeneration (ARMD) and retinitis pigmentosa (RP). Widely as the availability of micro-manufacturing being introduced into the building of novel interfaces for the nervous system, there are four approaches for visual prosthesis, which is currently being pursued, including the visual cortex, epiretinal and sub-retinal and optic nerve prostheses.

New hope in recent times has generated shows that electrical stimulation almost location along the visual path can evoke perceptions of visual perception called "phosphenes".

In the Figure (5.1) shows distribution studies areas of "visual prostheses" which will be explained later in subject of the "ongoing projects" .So that each color refers to the type of prosthesis developer or the study current it now.

Figure (5.1) World map that shows the global endeavor to develop of visual prostheses [64]

5.2 Some of Ongoing projects (currently):

5.2.1 CORTIVIS the European project (Cortical Visual Neuroprosthesis for the Blind) [65]

In year 2001, the Commission of the European Communities awarded the project financing CORTIVIS (QLK6-CT2001-00279).

Have contributed in this project (CORTIVIS): Six University laboratories , One technological research center and One company (SME) who they have experience in the development of high technology medical devices are combining their resources and efforts.

Coordinator:

University Miguel Hernández (Spain),Dr. Eduardo Fernandez

Research Groups:

- University of Granada (Spain), By Dr. Francisco Pelayo
- University of Oldenburg (Germany), Dr. Josef Ammermüller
- University of Vienna (Austria), Dr. Peter Ahnelt
- Centre National de la Research Scientifique (France),Dr. Lyle Graham
- University of Montpellier (France), Dr. Pierre Rabischong
- Biomedical Technologies, S.L (Spain), Dr. Francisco Garcia
- Instituto de Engenharia de Sistemas e Computadores (Portugal),Dr. Moises Piedade
- European Comission,Dr. Gesa Hansen and Dr. Carlos Bonhorst

The purpose of this project aims to develop models in the field of visual rehabilitation and demonstrate the feasibility of cortical neuroprosthesis, interfaced with the visual cortex, as a means through which a limited but useful visual sense may be restored to deeply blind people. Although the full restoration of vision seem impossible, and can distinguish the shape and location of objects allow blind subjects to ‘navigate’ in a familiar environment and to read expanded text, resulting in a significant improvement in the standard of living of blind and visually impaired persons.

This work targeted to stimulate the primary visual cortex, because the neurons in the upper regions of the brain (the visual cortex) and often escape from this decay. If these upper the visual centers can be stimulated with visual information in a similar format to some extent the way they were prior to stimulate the development of total blindness, it may be a blind person is able to use this stimulus to extract information about the physical world around him / her.

In Figure (5.2) illustrates the basic components of our approach (Neuroprosthesis visual cortical). The entire system will use the bioinspired (similar to the retina) and the processing of visual front-end, and is able to change the world in front of a blind person into electrical signals that can be used to excite, in real time the neurons in his / her visual cortex. Information resulting from this bioinspired peripheral device, and will be used to stimulate an array of penetrating electrodes implanted into the primary visual cortex. Such a visual neuroprosthesis is expected to recreate a limited, but useful visual sense in a blind individual who is using such a system.

Through multiple electrodes are intracortical study the safety and effectiveness of injecting a permanent charge in the cerebral cortex using histopathological and physiological techniques. And the development of a multichannel neurostimulators restructuring (Channels 128) capable of driving a current injection of different wavelength through of high impedance electrodes, as well as multi-channel transcutaneous power and data radiofrequency links to the microelectrodes intracortical.

Figure (5.2) the general structure of the visual prosthesis (CORTIVIS). [65]

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=nJEmMd55jZo>

The results of this project is to provide information concerning the neuro-prosthesis is not available at the present time, as well as new information about plastic changes in the adult nervous system, which has implications for rehabilitative training and development of the device. If we can understand more about the basic mechanisms of neural coding, and safely stimulate the nervous system, there will be a real possibility for the application of this knowledge clinically. Although we are still far from perfect visual prosthesis, the success of the cochlear implant looks very promising also neuro-technological for this application.

5.2.2 Argus Retinal Prosthesis

Has developed in (2002) the first version of the prosthesis Argus I in (Second Sight Medical Products, Sylmar, California), and clinically tested on 6 patients who suffering from several diseases inherited disease retinitis pigmentosa. The second version of the Argus II, has been tested for the first time in Mexico in (2006). After that, it was conducting a clinical trial of 30 patients in ten medical centers across Europe and the United States [66]. In March of 2011, the Argus II version of the system was approved for clinical and commercial use in the European Union.

The System Argus II Retinal Prosthesis (is an epiretinal device with an array of 60 electrodes) the external part of the Argus II Retinal Prosthesis System consists of a glasses-mounted camera and a battery-powered video-processing unit that is worn on the patient's body. The processing unit converts the camera-captured image into an electronic signal that is transmitted by cable to a transmitting coil located on the glasses. The implanted portion of the device (Figure 1) consists of a receiving coil that wirelessly receives information from an external transmitting coil and is sutured to the sclera by an encircling scleral band. Data are sent via a small transcleral cable from the transmitting coil to the electrode array, which is firmly held to the retinal surface by a specialized tack. The array is a 6 x 10 grid of electrodes, with each electrode emitting electric pulses directly to the retinal surface. Directretinal electric stimulation leads to a nerve response that is transmitted via the optic nerve to the visual cortex. This allows the patient to perceive spots of light. The maximum visual field obtainable with the Argus II System is approximately 20 degrees. [67]

Figure (5.3):(A) A photograph of the external portion of the Argus II prosthesis system including glasses-mounted video camera, radio frequency (RF) coil, and Video Processing Unit (VPU) with rechargeable battery.

(B) A photograph of the implanted portion of Argus II prosthesis system including the 6×10 electrode array, electronics case, and implant RF coil. [67]

Currently, the resolution is limited, as the device has 60 pixels. Could enable patients with progressive, hereditary disease retinitis pigmentosa, who previously could see little or no light, to read large letters, determine the location of moving objects or people, and detect street curbs.

Figure (5.4) as shown in the image increasing resolution.

<http://www.brightfocus.org/macular/brightfocus-insights/macular-degeneration-artificial-retina.html>

Patients who have lost central vision due to age-related macular degeneration would not likely experience much benefit from an Argus II because their peripheral vision is still better than that provided by the device. However, further advances in chip technology may increase the level of vision. Second Sight is planning to increase the number of electrodes to 240 in a future model. The German company Retinal Implant, has begun clinical testing with a 1,500-pixel device. For reference, a healthy human eye has the equivalent of approximately 1 million “pixels.”

5.2.3 Microsystem-based Visual Prosthesis (MIVP)

The micro-systems based visual prosthesis for optic nerve stimulation (MIVIP) has started in 1st December 1996, and has been completed in 30 September 2000. [68]

Designed by Belgian Professor Claude Veraart when he told a news conference.

“We have implanted (the device) in two patients so far,” Veraart from the Catholic University of Louvain-la-Neuve near Brussels said. This is a spiral cuff electrode around the optic nerve at the back of the eye. It is connected to a stimulator implanted in a small depression in the skull. The stimulator receives signals from an externally worn camera, which are translated into electrical signals that stimulate the optic nerve directly which passes the information to the brain. This technology could help people with the retinal disease and macular degeneration.

Generates (MIVIP) visual perceptions much less from safety and stimulator saturation limits. These perceptions called "phosphenes" , are of reasonably small size and are broadly distributed in the visual field. They can thus be used to convey useful visual information. The results obtained so far still support the potential usefulness of the optic nerve visual prosthesis. A low-resolution artificial vision can be expected from the prosthesis after extensive training.

Figure (5.5) the micro-systems based visual prosthesis for optic nerve stimulation.

http://www.medgadget.com/2005/02/good_news_from.html

5.2.4 Implantable Miniature Telescope (IMT)

Implantable miniature telescope (IMT) procedure intended to improve vision in people with end-stage age-related macular degeneration (AMD). End-stage AMD causes central vision loss in both eyes and is a major cause of blindness and visual impairment in adults above 50 years of age.

Created by VisionCare Ophthalmic Technologies in conjunction with the CentraSight Treatment Program, (IMT) is a micro-optical device as small as a pea that is implanted in one eye, replacing the natural lens and providing an image that has been magnified more than twofold, thus improving visual acuity. The non-implanted eye provides peripheral vision for mobility and orientation. This type of device is implanted in the eye's posterior chamber and works by increasing (by about three times) the size of the image projected onto the retina in order to overcome a centrally located scotoma or blind spot.

IMT is indicated for patients of 75 years of age or older with stable severe to profound vision impairment caused by bilateral central scotomas (blind areas) associated with end-stage AMD. [69]

Figure (5.6) show size of IMT. [69]

5.2.5 Tübingen MPDA Project Alpha IMS

A Southern German group guided by the University Eye Hospital in Tübingen, was created in 1995 by Eberhart Zrenner to create a subretinal prosthesis. The chip is found beyond the retina and uses micro-photodiode collections (MPDA) that gather event light and change it in to electronic current arousing the retinal ganglion cells. The German group commenced in vivo trials in 2000, as evoked cortical possibilities remained calculated as of Yucatán micro pigs and Rabbits. In 2010 a spic-and-span multicenter Study has been commenced utilizing a completely implantable implement with 1500 Electrodes Alpha IMS (produced by Retina Implant AG, Reutlingen, Germany), 10 cases contained thus far; first outcomes have been offered at ARVO 2011.

5.2.6 Artificial Silicon Retina (ASR)

The brothers Alan Chow and Vincent Chow have developed a microchip containing 3500 photo diodes, which detect light and convert it into electrical impulses, which stimulate healthy retinal ganglion cells. The ASR requires no externally worn devices. To determine the safety and efficacy of the artificial silicon retina (ASR) microchip implanted in the subretinal space to treat vision loss from retinitis pigmentosa. Where the ASR microchip is a 2-mm-diameter silicon-based device that contains approximately 5000 microelectrode-tipped microphotodiodes and is powered by incident light, that each have their own stimulating electrode.[70]

5.2.7 Photovoltaic Retinal Prosthesis

Daniel Palanker and his group at Stanford University have developed a photovoltaic system for visual prosthesis that includes a subretinal photodiode array and an infrared image projection system mounted on video goggles. Data stream from a video camera is processed by a pocket PC, and the resulting images are displayed on a head-mounted micro-display, similar to video goggles. From the micro-display the images are projected onto retina using pulsed (1-10 ms) near-infrared (~900 nm) light. These light pulses are photovoltaically converted into bi-phasic pulses of electric current flowing between the active and return electrode in each pixel, which stimulates the nearby inner retinal neurons, and thereby introduces visual information into the retinal neural network. [71]

Figure (5.7) Elements of Photovoltaic Retinal Prosthesis. [71]

5.2.8 Bionic Vision Australia

Bionic Vision Australia is a national consortium of researchers brings together a cross-disciplinary group of world-leading experts in the fields of ophthalmology, biomedical engineering, electrical engineering and materials science, neuroscience, vision science, psychophysics, wireless integrated-circuit design, and surgical, preclinical and clinical practice who are working together to develop bionic eye devices to restore a sense of vision to people with profound vision loss because of age-related macular degeneration and retinitis pigmentosa that led by Professor Anthony Burkitt . The Wide-View device, includes the new technology with the materials which have been successfully in the other clinical implants. This method contains a new microchip using 98 stimulating electrodes and it aims to provide enhanced mobility for individuals patients to aid them move safely and correctly in their environment. This implant is going to be placed in the suprachoroidal space.

The device aims to provide functional central vision to assist with tasks such as reading large print and face recognition. This high-acuity implant will be inserted epiretinally. The Bionic Vision Australia consortium is concurrently make developing the High-Acuity Device, which is incorporates a number of new technologies to bring together a microchip and an implant with 1024 electrodes.

The prototype consists of a camera, attached to a pair of glasses which sends the signal to the implanted microchip in epiretinal, to stimulate the remaining healthy neurons in the retina it is converted into electrical impulses. This information is then passed on to the optic nerve and the vision processing centres of the brain. Where the patients individuals with retinitis pigmentosa will be the first to participate in the studies, followed by age-related macular degeneration. [72]

5.2.9 The Virtual Retinal Display (VRD)

It is laser-based system for projecting an image directly on the retina. This may be useful for enhancing or improve normal vision or bypassing an occlusion such as a damaged cornea or a cataract. The goal of the program was to discover a noninvasive and highly accurate way to detect retinal diseases. VRD used a pen-based computer program. [73]

Figure (5.8) [73]

As well as each of these projects, which are being studied and developed, but cannot dispense from the old alternatives in this time until to get satisfactory results, such as (white canes, guide dogs and sonar glasses, etc).

Chapter six: General conclusions

6.1 Conclusion

This work presents some of the anatomic and physiologic bases for the eye and artificial vision, In spite of simplicity of this work, In addition to the studies currently around the world, discusses the status of several approaches to restoring functional vision in the blind, describes some of the biological and engineering issues facing developers of these systems. In general these approaches to artificial vision demonstrate at some level that it is possible to manufacture an interface to the target neural structure, implant the stimulating device, and evoke visual sensation via passing electric currents. Intractable medical conditions may be treated by the visual prostheses. The visual perceptions which are created may not have same details of natural vision, and there is ample evidence that individuals who apply to these devices can learn to reduce the use of the inputs to implement simple tasks. Further development will be necessary for these visual prostheses to allow an improvement in the quality of life for blind individuals. The quest remains for the ability to restore useful vision in blind individuals and with advances in biomechanical engineering this may become a possibility in the not too distant future. The visual prosthesis is a radical and innovative approach in restoring vision to individuals who exposed to accidents and lost their eyesight or some diseases that cause blindness or visual impairment such as (cataracts, glaucoma, macular degeneration, retinitis pigmentosa and retinal detachment etc...). There are many advances in the treatment of diseases which result in visual impairment. These treatments prevent or limit the extent of visual impairment but it is not a final solution or provide an opportunity for those who lost their sight fully.

6.2 Future Work

Which pay an attention how many groups and laboratories have joined the field of visual prosthesis development over the past 1 to 2 decades, and how many publications about methodology, designs, and engineering of visual prosthetics have appeared at professional conferences. And how it could be developed in the future.

Vision restoration through the retinal, cortical implants and optic nerve is no longer just the stuff of fantasy. The design and development of visual prostheses rapidly move from the engineering phase toward preclinical and clinical trials, there are good news gives hope to those who suffer from fully blindness, the clinical reports demonstrated so far varying successes, with all patients report at least some sensation of the light, spot light called (phosphenes), and a smaller proportion gaining more detailed visual function, such as identifying patterns of light, dark areas and edge detection.

Visual prostheses that allow users to explore the environment ‘naturally’, with eye movements (as in sub-retinal implants transforming incident light into electric currents ‘in-situ’) could allow for better performance than systems where the environment has to be explored with head movements (as in epi-retinal implants that use external head-mounted cameras). Although there are many challenges biological and physiological for future experiments.

Additional simulations on normal subjects could still provide important information on image features and additional processing that could help improve performance (i.e. contrast enhancement, edge detection). Furthermore, particular isolated subtasks (i.e. motion detection thresholds) could still be studied in more detail. However, this knowledge is not essential to understanding visual function with an artificial vision device, and would not fundamentally change the minimum requirements determined in the studies.

There is an urgent demand for the miracle cure for blindness. Visual prosthetics are unlikely to be that cure, just like hearing by a cochlear implant is far from normal hearing. But if there is bring the visual prosthesis to a level where it can measure up to today's cochlear prosthesis, that

will be a tremendous accomplishment. For the time being, this can be a tangible and very worthwhile goal.

Finally, at this point it is imperative that a substantial research effort is made to better define the characteristics of transmission around the electrode-nerve interface (spatial selectivity, stimulation thresholds, retinotopy of the perceived stimulus). More in particular, fundamental knowledge will depend on the results of psychophysical experiments on blind subjects both in acute and chronic trials.

Chapter seven: References

7 References

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